

Quality assessment checklist

The quality assessment criteria (QA) are specified below in four different categories:

- **Generic:**

- QA 1. Are the aims clearly stated? YES/NO
- QA 2. Are the study participants or observational units adequately described?
YES/NO/PARTIAL
- QA 3. Was the study design appropriate with respect to research aim?
YES/NO/PARTIAL
- QA 4. Are the data collection methods adequately described?
YES/NO/PARTIAL
- QA 5. Are the statistical methods justified by the author? YES/NO
- QA 6. Are the statistical methods used to analyze the data properly described and
referenced? YES/NO
- QA 7. Are negative findings presented? YES/NO/PARTIAL
- QA 8. Are all the study questions answered? YES/NO
- QA 9. Do the researchers explain future implications? YES/NO

- **Survey**

- QA 10. Was the denominator (i.e. the population size) reported? YES/NO
- QA 11. Did the author justify the sample size? YES/NO
- QA 12. Is the sample representative of the population to which the results will
generalize? YES/NO
- QA 13. Have “dropouts” introduced biases on result limitation? YES/NO/NOT
APPLICABLE

- **Experiment**

- QA 14. Were treatments randomly allocated? YES/NO
- QA 15. If there is a control group, are participants similar to the treatment group
participants in terms of variables that may affect study outcomes? YES/NO
- QA 16. Could the lack of blinding introduce bias? YES/NO
- QA 17. Are the variables used in the study adequately measured (i.e. are the variables
likely to be valid and reliable)? YES/NO

- **Case Study**

- QA 18. Is the case study context defined? YES/NO
- QA 19. Are sufficient raw data presented to provide an understanding of the case?
YES/NO
- QA 20. Is the case study based on theory and linked to existing literature? YES/NO
- QA 21. Are ethical issues addressed properly (personal intentions, integrity issues,
consent, review board approval)? YES/NO
- QA 22. Is a clear Chain of evidence established from observations to conclusions?
YES/NO/PARTIAL

- **Experience Report**

- QA 23. Is the focus of the study reported? YES/NO
- QA 24. Does the author report personal observation? YES/NO
- QA 25. Is there a link between data, interpretation and conclusion?
YES/NO/PARTIAL

QA 26.Does the study report multiple experiences? YES/NO

The procedure of scoring for quality assessment questions is as follows:

- 1 for Yes.
- 0.5 for Partly.
- 0 for No.